

The 21st Amendment: Decoding Military Hegemony in Pakistan's Anti-Terrorism Framework and Political Landscape

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ABSTRACT

This paper critically examines the establishment of military courts under Pakistan's 21st Constitutional Amendment, analyzing its implications for democratic governance, civil-military relations, and judicial independence. The amendment, introduced as a counterterrorism measure following the 2014 Army Public School attack, has sparked intense debate regarding its constitutionality and effectiveness. While supporters argue that military courts provide swift justice, critics highlight concerns over lack of transparency, human rights violations, and erosion of civilian judicial authority. Employing a qualitative research approach, this study integrates semi-structured interviews, document analysis, and media narrative assessment to explore the amendment's broader implications. Findings suggest that the parliamentary endorsement of military courts was influenced by military pressure and public sentiment, raising questions about legislative autonomy. The study also reveals that non-availability of data on acquittals and convictions, coupled with ISPR's strategic communication efforts, has shaped public perception while limiting independent scrutiny. Moreover, the research underscores the high confession rates (over 90%) in military courts, pointing to potential coercion and due process violations. While military courts were initially sanctioned as a temporary measure, their extension beyond the original two-year mandate indicates structural inefficiencies in Pakistan's civilian judiciary. The study argues for a gradual transition towards comprehensive judicial reforms, strengthening the civilian-led counterterrorism framework while safeguarding fundamental rights. Ultimately, the research highlights the pressing need for transparency, accountability, and adherence to democratic norms in Pakistan's approach to counterterrorism policy.

KEYWORDS

Military Courts, Democracy, Pakistan, Fundamental Rights, Parliament

1. Introduction

Indeed, the barbaric attack on Army Public School (APS) had far-reaching impact on the minds of many especially in counter-terrorism measures of immediate nature. The military courts under the 21st Constitutional Amendment, no doubt, have been welcomed by the public in response to their emotional and psychological resentment. However, it has posted many debates across the political and democratic spheres. Clearly, such civil-military discussion under democracy in Pakistan is nothing new but a consistent phenomenon since inception. Yet, the military courts under the 21st Amendment have raised the debates with different and conflicting dynamics and political interpretation. Generally, the military courts are supposed to deal the

misconduct of army personnel within prescribed domain as mentioned in Pakistan's Constitution and Pakistan's Army Act 1952 (Ali, 2022). The dilemma of concern in this scenario of military courts has of grave nature, since it was the Parliament of Pakistan which has rendered the civilian supremacy and democratic norms before Pakistan's military establishment (Baig, 2020).

As a part of "National Action Plan" to combat the terrorism, the military courts were approved by Pakistan Muslim League Nawaz's (PML-N) party for the period of two years initially which later on was further extended under the 23rd Constitutional Amendment. Interestingly, the Pakistan's People Party (PPP) was also party to the approval of military courts even though both PPP and PML-N had

signed “Charter of Democracy” in 2006 during Musharraf’s era (Bilal Hassan, 2018). Though there was minor criticism by a few members of both parties against the 21st Amendment, however, overall, both parties seemed helpless or failed to safeguard the supremacy of the Constitution of Pakistan and democratic norms in general. It seemed that these parties have no clear strategy or policy of counter-terrorism measures as many states in Northern America and Europe had achieved such objectives without violating the democratic norms (Hassan, 2022). In layman sense, could it have not possible to equip and improve the civil judiciary and related departments through new legislation and policy framework to overcome the menace of terrorism.

There are multiple aspects of this discussion where the military courts can be dealt with democratic practices i.e., open trial, right to justice, the role of Parliament and civil departments, civil judiciary and many more. However, this Paper is aimed at four basic factors which have conflicting nature with democratic norms and military courts establishment. First, it analyzes the fact and response of different interviewees in the realm of Parliament relations with the military establishment at the time of passing the 21st Amendment. Whether the Parliament of Pakistan failed to deliver a conclusive approach of counter-terrorism policy and therefore, they opted the military policy, or the Parliament of Pakistan was under pressure from general masses and Army bureaucracy to surrender the civil rights of judgments (Munir, 2022). This matrix can be helpful to break-down the complexity of civil-military relationship which became the first and root cause of the establishment of military courts under the 21st Amendment.

Second, the focus is given on finding the real force behind the policy, idea, and establishment of military courts. Many are of the view that the establishment of military courts was the messy competition between the civil and military spheres to gain maximum influence in governmental affairs. This asymmetric competition, in past, has been the bitter reality of Pakistani politics (Zubair, 2019), therefore, the possibility in this case scenario can also be analyzed. To get a clear picture of such competition

in the 21st Amendment, question has been asked from all respondents to shed light on this subject matter as well.

Third, the ISPR stance in support of 21st amendment is analyzed. Though, rhetoric ISPR has placed before general masses and policy stakeholder was an outstanding approach which had convinced many. However, the offensive defense nature of the ISPR stance in the establishment of military courts has some short comings as well which have been discussed in this paper with different variables.

Lastly, this Paper has given focus on the issue of non-availability of actual data of acquittal/conviction done by military courts. Democracy and fair trial demand the openness of all the data of accused in any case. Since the military courts failed to do so, the questions of fair trial and justice have to come to many minds. Such complex and confused questions have first break into different themes and then analyzed to come to a meaningful sense of the phenomenon.

2. Methodology

This study employs a qualitative research approach to examine the establishment of military courts under Pakistan's 21st Constitutional Amendment and its implications for democratic norms. The research design follows an exploratory-descriptive framework, seeking to understand the interplay between civil-military relations, parliamentary decision-making, and the broader socio-political dynamics surrounding the 21st Amendment.

3. Data Collection Methods

Primary Data: The study primarily relies on semi-structured interviews with legal professionals, academics, journalists, parliamentarians, research society members, and law enforcement officials. The purposive sampling technique was employed to select respondents with expertise in constitutional law, democratic governance, and counterterrorism policies. Due to the low response rate, a snowball sampling strategy was adopted to identify more participants (Alfred, 1987). This data was analyzed through meticulous use of SPSS.

Secondary Data: The research also incorporates document analysis of legislative debates, court rulings, policy papers, and reports from governmental and non-governmental organizations. Media narrative analysis was conducted to assess the framing of military courts in national discourse (Gerring, 2001). The role of Inter-Services Public Relations (ISPR) in shaping public opinion was examined through content analysis of official statements and media briefings.

Data Analysis Methods

Thematic Analysis: Responses from interviews were coded and analyzed thematically to identify recurring patterns in civil-military relations, legislative motivations, and public perceptions of military courts ((Babbie, 1986).

Discourse Analysis: The study scrutinized parliamentary speeches, media coverage, and legal commentaries to assess the rationale behind the 21st Amendment ((Baig, 2020).

Comparative Analysis: The Pakistani military court framework was compared to international legal standards and precedents, drawing on human rights reports and judicial rulings ((ICJ, 2019).

Limitations

- The sensitivity of the topic led to low response rates, affecting the generalizability of the findings.
- The lack of official transparency on military court proceedings posed challenges in acquiring verifiable data.
- Time and resource constraints limited the inclusion of a broader respondent pool.

4. Results

The pivotal aspect of the study focused on the scrupulous selection of interviewees. Targeting six distinct professions renowned for their profound expertise, a total of 101 advocates from the Supreme Court and high courts were approached, aiming to glean insights into the 21st Amendment and the procedural intricacies surrounding military court convictions dealing the cases of the convicts which have been trailed under military courts. These

interviews not only provided a nuanced understanding of the legal aspects of Constitution and the place of military courts and its jurisdiction, and it also offered valuable perspectives on the Parliament's role in the framing of the 21st Amendment, the ISPR and how it deals the Policy stakeholders and general masses. The second-largest cohort comprised 85 academicians, followed by the journalist community, encompassing 78 interviewees, constituted the third-largest group, selected for their role in shaping public and policymakers' perceptions and offering insights into the civil-military establishment's involvement in the 21st Amendment's passage.

Also, 39 Parliamentarians were interviewed to unravel the democratic underpinnings behind the approval of seemingly undemocratic trends. Similarly, Research Societies, with 13 interviewees, aided in comprehending the scope of democratic practice and the active/passive role of parliamentarians during the whole process of legislation. Finally, law enforcement agencies, represented by four interviewees, were included to explore the intricate relationship between democratic practices and military courts.

Below mentioned Table-A summarizes the details of responses from respondents:

Profession	Approach ed by No	Approach ed by %	Non- responde nt by no	Non- responde nt by %
Legal Fraternity	101	32	80	28
Academicians	85	27	79	28
Journalists	78	24	72	26
Parliamentari ans	39	12	38	14
Research Societies	13	04	08	03
Law Enforcement Agencies	04	00	04	00

The observed response rate for the research emerges as notably low, with a mere 39 out of 320 approached interviewees consenting to participate, reflecting a response rate of only 13%. A substantial majority, constituting 87% of those approached, declined engagement in the study. This low response rate could potentially be attributed to two primary explanations. Firstly, interviewees may have

harbored apprehensions about discussing the sensitive subject matter concerning anti-terrorism laws and their implications for Fundamental Rights in Pakistan. The delicacy of the topic might have dissuaded some from active participation. Secondly, there is a possibility that certain

interviewees did not perceive a sense of obligation or responsibility to partake in the study, contributing to the overall diminished response rate. These dual factors could have played a significant role in shaping the observed participation patterns.

Following are the profession wise number and percentage ratios of respondents and non-respondents in Table B:

Profession	Responded in No	Responded in %	Non responded in No	Non responded in %
Legal Fraternity	21	21	80	79
Academicians	06	07	79	93
Journalists	06	08	72	92
Parliamentarians	01	03	38	97
Research Societies	05	38	08	62
Law Enforcement Agencies	00	00	04	100

The low response rate among the approached interviewees in this study cautions against drawing definitive conclusions regarding their views on the topic. The refusals to participate, often attributed to reasons such as fear or perceived lack of responsibility, present a notable challenge in gauging the perspectives of the target population. Notably, instances were observed where interviewees, like an anchor person at a local news-based TV channel, initially agreed to an interview but later declined upon reviewing the topic. Similar patterns emerged with various other interviewees employing diverse tactics and reactions to evade participation. Moreover, some interviewees, particularly those approached online, remained entirely unresponsive. In navigating these challenges, the researchers adhered to ethical principles by anonymizing the 92 interviewees who declined participation and diligently substituted them with new interviewees from the same professional background. Despite these efforts, the response rate persisted unexpectedly low, underscoring the complexity of engaging participants in discussions surrounding the sensitive subject matter.

5. Discussion

The contest for authority between the civil and military establishments within Pakistan has exerted a substantial impact on the nation's legal and political trajectory. A strategic implementation of the diversionary theory of war

has been observed, serving as a tactic to shift focus away from domestic concerns and validate the actions of the ruling class. This has resulted in a disregard for pivotal issues such as development, prosperity, and accountability. Despite encountering challenges, positive strides have been made in reinstating and fortifying the democratic process, along with initiatives aimed at augmenting governance and accountability. Nonetheless, the persistent power struggle among various factions remains a formidable impediment. Consequently, it remains imperative to persist in advocating for democracy, supporting the enhancement of governance, and addressing fundamental instigators of instability such as poverty, inequality, and corruption. This concerted effort is essential to pave the way for a more stable and reasoned approach in countering terrorism.

The historical record unmistakably illustrates that the involvement of figures such as Zia and Musharraf in Afghanistan's Jihad and the War on Terror has contributed to a persistent terrorism issue in Pakistan's tribal regions. The 2014 Army Public School attack in Peshawar served as a catalyst for political consensus, leading to the establishment of military courts as a response to the prevailing terrorism threat. Recognizing the imperative to prioritize "might not right" in the Constitution, democratically elected parliamentarians endorsed the 21st Amendment. However, this approval unveiled a fundamental flaw in the Country's policy-making process, highlighting a reactive stance toward

crises rather than proactive policy development. The National Action Plan proposed military courts as a temporary solution, coupled with a two-year timeframe for essential reforms in anti-terrorism institutions and the criminal justice system.

The recurrent misapplication of the Constitution in the realm of counterterrorism initiatives, including the implementation of anti-terrorism legislation, has been conspicuous. The military establishment has persistently advocated for the trial of terrorism suspects in military courts, notwithstanding political opposition. Insights from interview data underscore a sense of skepticism regarding the credibility of parliamentarians, with 23 percent of

respondents expressing reservations about the autonomy of the Parliament in endorsing the 21st Amendment. According to political analysts, the military establishment exerted significant influence in securing the amendment's approval, shedding light on the intricacies and challenges inherent in Pakistan's legislative processes (Baig, 2020). The interview data unequivocally highlights the delicacy of parliamentary affairs and underscores the prevailing dominance of the military establishment in this context. For instance, 23 percent of interviewees expressed dissent regarding the notion that the parliament was genuinely free in passing the 21st Amendment.

Chart 01: Percentage ratio of disagreement of Parliament free-will in passing 21st Amendment.

The military's notable influence in the passage of the 21st Amendment, despite resistance from parliamentarians, is apparent in various statements issued by political representatives both prior to and following its ratification. Former Chairman Senate Mian Raza Rabbani conveyed his dismay, expressing, "Although I have been in the Senate for more than 12 years, today, I have never been as ashamed as I am today, and I cast my vote against my conscience" (Dawn, 2015). This sentiment found resonance with two political parties, Jamiat Ulema-e-Islam (Maulana Fazlur Rehman) and Jamaat-e-Islami (led by Siraj ul Haq), both of which refrained from participating in both the Senate session and the voting process.

In addressing the issue of terrorism, the imperative need for a prompt and efficient justice system, effective prosecution processes, and resilient, independent justice institutions is evident. However, Pakistan has encountered challenges in establishing such a system and lacks comprehensive policies for the prevention of terrorism. The creation of military courts through the 21st Amendment has been criticized as an insufficient solution to these challenges. When respondents were questioned about the reasons behind the establishment of military courts, 36 percent asserted that political interests, rather than devising effective strategies for curbing terrorism, drove the conception of the 21st Amendment. Meanwhile, 51 percent expressed support for the idea that establishing military courts is an effective

means of controlling terrorism. Similarly, 13 percent of respondents acknowledged that expeditious justice could mitigate the existing menace and the brutal killing of

innocents, hence considering the institution of military courts as pivotal to achieving this goal.

Chart 02: Percentage ratios of causes of Military Courts establishment

In spite of some arguments in favor of the 21st Amendment, military courts have faced considerable criticism from a variety of sources. Critics have voiced concerns about human rights violations, the structure and operation of military courts, and the military establishment's inability to present a coherent and reasoned approach to both the public and the international community. When assessing the rhetoric and arguments supporting the 21st

Amendment by the military establishment during its initial phase, respondents exhibited a mixed perception. Approximately 51 percent perceived the military establishment's behavior as aggressive, while 28 percent viewed it as apologetic. These disparate perceptions underscore a sense of ambiguity, with only 21 percent of respondents considering the military's approach to military courts and public discourse as sound and rational.

Chart 03: Army Responses in Support of Military Courts in Percentage Ratio

Various factors contribute to the paucity of information and transparency surrounding the operations and

convictions of military courts under the 21st Amendment. A significant concern is the exclusive dependence on the Inter-

Services Public Relations (ISPR) as the sole source of information on this matter, giving rise to criticisms of the amendment and fostering apprehensions about the military's involvement in politics. Respondents interviewed expressed frustration with the lack of clarity and proper record-keeping regarding individuals convicted under the military-led criminal justice system. Notably, 44 percent of respondents concurred that many missing persons are likely

to have been convicted or are anticipated to face convictions through military courts. In the midst of ongoing regional challenges, such as the transition in Afghanistan and the AUKUS agreement, the Pakistan military is urged to refrain from exacerbating existing issues. Furthermore, some respondents posit that the absence of concrete data on military court convictions is rooted in accountability issues.

Chart 04: Reasons of non-availability of data of convicts by military courts

Another concern revolves around the qualifications of military judges, as there is no explicit requirement for them to possess a law degree. In addition, a December 2016 press release by the ISPR disclosed a high confession rate in military courts, exceeding 90%, with 135 out of 144 convicted individuals admitting to their crimes (Omer, Suspect confessions, 2016). This notably elevated confession rate has aroused suspicions among various human rights observers. The International Court of Justice (ICJ) has underscored that suspects undergoing trials in military courts remain in military custody even after their confessions are recorded by magistrates. This lack of access to the outside world renders them more vulnerable to torture, ill-treatment, and external pressure or coercion. Allegedly, some suspects were covertly detained by military authorities as early as 2010 and held in internment centers in the Federally Administered Tribal Areas (FATA) until they

confessed to their crimes during military trials (Omer, Suspect confessions, 2016).

6. Conclusion

The establishment of military courts under Pakistan's 21st Constitutional Amendment has stirred debates and raised crucial questions regarding the nation's democratic norms and counter-terrorism strategies. The paper examined four essential factors contributing to the complexity of this issue. Firstly, the parliamentary response to the amendment reflects a dilemma wherein the civilian supremacy and democratic norms were seemingly compromised, prompting questions about the role and pressures faced by the Parliament.

Secondly, the paper delves into the competitive dynamics between the civil and military spheres, exploring the possibility that the establishment of military courts is a result of messy competition for influence in governmental affairs. Such asymmetrical competition, a historical reality in

Pakistani politics, is analyzed to understand its role in shaping the military court policy.

Thirdly, the study scrutinizes the stance of the Inter-Services Public Relations (ISPR) in support of the 21st Amendment. While the ISPR's rhetoric convinced many, the paper highlights the offensive defense nature of its stance, identifying shortcomings that warrant consideration.

Lastly, the non-availability of actual data on acquittals and convictions by military courts is explored, posing challenges to principles of democracy and fair trial. The paper dissects this issue to shed light on the complex questions surrounding justice and fairness within the military court system. In conclusion, this study contributes to a nuanced understanding of the multifaceted aspects surrounding the establishment of military courts, emphasizing the need for transparency, accountability, and careful consideration of democratic principles in counter-terrorism measures.

This paper is based on data collected during PhD and use of LLM is acknowledged.

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